

POSSIBILITY OF OBSERVING PARITY NONCONSERVATION IN X-RAY SPECTRA OF HEAVY ATOMS

Melibayev M.

Associate Professor of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14010730>

Abstract. *The space parity-violation effects that occur in the atomic x-ray spectra of Mo, W, Au, and U in the presence of electron-nuclear weak currents are considered. The quantities characterizing the degree of parity violation are of the order of $\sim 10^{-7}$. Partial estimates of the experimental possibilities of detecting the effect are considered.*

Keywords: *neutral weak current, space parity, asymmetry, forbidden transition, magnate and electrical dipol transition, neutral bosons.*

Introduction

Weak neutral current interactions are one of the ways in which subatomic particles can interact by means of the weak force. These interactions are mediated by the neutral Z- W^0 boson. The discovery of weak neutral currents was a significant step toward the unification of electromagnetism and the weak force into the electroweak force, and led to the discovery of the W and Z bosons.

Exchange of a Z boson transfers momentum, spin, and energy, but leaves the interacting particles' quantum numbers unaffected – charge, flavor, baryon number, lepton number, etc. Because there is no transfer of electrical charge involved, exchange of Z particles is referred to as "neutral" in the phrase "neutral current". However, the word "current" here has nothing to do with electricity – it simply refers to the exchange of the Z particle.

Neutral atoms are easily available objects for investigation. Calculations of parity-violation effects can be performed for the inner shells of atoms with a sufficient degree of accuracy. This makes it possible, in the case of experimental detection of parity-violation effects, to reach unambiguous conclusions about the magnitude and sign of the constant for neutral weak currents [1-8].

Formulation of the problem and main results

Parity violation in decays of atoms and ions can be detected from the appearance of circular polarization of the radiation or from the asymmetry in the emission of photons and photoelectrons with respect to the direction of the initial polarization of the atom. [8-9]. The degree of parity violation is defined by the expression

$$iP = \frac{2 \langle V \rangle}{\Delta E} \sqrt{\frac{W_1}{W_0}} \quad (1)$$

where $\langle V \rangle$ is the matrix element of the effective weak interaction operator, which mixes states of opposite parity, ΔE is the energy interval between these states (we assume that, effectively, only two states are mixed), W_0 is the probability of the basic transition with neglect of the weak interaction, and W_1 is the probability of the transition from the level hybridized by the weak interaction.

The effective potential of the electron-nuclear weak interaction for the atom or ion has the form (in units with $\hbar = c = 1$)

$$V^{en} = \frac{G}{\sqrt{2}} \Sigma \left(g_1^{en} \cdot \gamma_5^{(e)} + g_2^{en} \boldsymbol{\alpha}^{\rightarrow(e)} \boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(n)} \right) \delta(\mathbf{r}) \quad (2)$$

where n is the number of electrons in the atom, $\gamma_5^{(e)}$, $\boldsymbol{\alpha}^{\rightarrow(e)}$ are Dirac matrices acting on the electron wave functions, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}^{(n)}$ is the spin of the nucleus, G is the Fermi weak-interaction constant, g_1^{en} and g_2^{en} are certain constants, depending on the number of protons (Z) and neutrons (N) in the nucleus. In the Weinberg model

$$g_1(Z, N) = Z(1 - (N + Z) / 2Z - 2\text{Sin}^2\theta_w) \quad (3)$$

where θ_w is a free parameter? The constant g_2^{en} depends on the angular-momentum coupling in the nucleus. From the data of the latest neutrino experiments $\text{Sin}^2\theta_w = 0.25$. [8,11].

It follows from (1) that we must look for cases in which levels of opposite parity are close together and must use the forbidden transitions from these levels to lower-lying levels. We have ascertained the relative positions of the energy levels from the data of [12]. In the Table we give the value of ΔE for some of the most favorable situations. For the basic transition we have selected the magnetic-dipole M1 transition K- L_I , where K ($1s_{1/2}$) and L_I ($2s_{1/2}$) are respectively the initial and final hole states. The level nearest to L_I , with the opposite parity is L_{II} ($2p_{1/2}$)

The amplitude of the one-quantum transition with allowance for the weak interaction is depicted in Figs. a and b. On mixing of the levels L_I and L_{II} ($2p_{1/2}$) by the weak interaction, owing to the interference of the amplitudes of the basic (a) and E1 – electrical dipole hybrid (b) transitions, the final photons acquire circular polarization.

Fig. 1. Feynman graphs corresponding to the basic transition and hybrid transition in the ion.

TABLE 1

Element	ΔE a.u.	W_0, s^{-1}	W_1, s^{-1}	$ P $
Mo	7.10	$3.02 \cdot 10^{10}$	$1.47 \cdot 10^{15}$	$1.49 \cdot 10^{-5}$
W	20.60	$1.33 \cdot 10^{13}$	$1.65 \cdot 10^{16}$	$0.64 \cdot 10^{-7}$
Au	23.95	$2.75 \cdot 10^{13}$	$2.18 \cdot 10^{16}$	$0.83 \cdot 10^{-7}$
U	31.53	$1,55 \cdot 10^{13}$	$4.16 \cdot 10^{16}$	$2.24 \cdot 10^{-7}$

Here, i is 2s, f - 1s, and j is 2p. Z- W^0 is the intermediate boson and N is the nucleus.

The probability of emission of a photon with polarization \mathbf{e} in the direction \mathbf{n} is equal to

$$W(\mathbf{n}, \mathbf{e}) = W_0 (1 + P(\mathbf{nS})), \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{S} = -i[\mathbf{e} * \mathbf{X} \mathbf{e}]$ is the photon spin. For the transition probabilities $W_0 = W(K - L_I)$ and $W_1 (K - L_{II})$ we have used the data of the relativistic calculations of [12,13]. The values of W_0 , and W_1 for the transitions that we are considering are given in the Table 1 [13].

The results were checked by analytic calculations with Coulomb wave functions, which should give the correct results for S for one-electron ions and the inner shells of heavy atoms.

The high intensity of the basic 4 transition (W_0) for large values of Z should be noted, and is an important advantage of the experiments on heavy atoms.

The details of the calculation of the matrix elements of the weak interaction (2) between the relativistic wave functions are given in [9,10]. Using the same methods of calculation for the matrix elements $\langle V \rangle$, we can obtain the following final expression

$$\langle n'j'l'm' | V | njlm \rangle = -\frac{G}{4\pi\sqrt{2}} g_1(Z, N) \quad (5)$$

$$\times \{ R_0(n'j'l'; nj\bar{l}) - R_0(n'j'\bar{l}'; njl) \} \delta_{l, \bar{l}},$$

where

$$R_0(n'j'l'; \bar{n}j\bar{l}) = \lim_{r \rightarrow 0} g_{n'j'l'}(r) f_{nj\bar{l}}(r),$$

here, $g_{n'j'l'}$ and $f_{nj\bar{l}}(r)$ are the upper and lower radial components of the Dirac wave function; $njlm$ are the single electron quantum numbers. A bar above the letter l implies the replacement $\bar{l} \rightarrow 2j - l$, and a bar above njl implies replacement of $g_{n'j'l'}$ by $f_{nj\bar{l}}(r)$.

In the calculation of the limit in (5) it is necessary to take into account the finite size of the nucleus. For the radial functions g and f we have used the Dirac self-consistent field functions obtained with the aid of the RAINE program. [14].

This program takes the finite size of the nucleus into account. The results of the calculations are given in the Table. The high intensity of the basic transition (W_0) for large values of Z should be noted, and is an important advantage of the experiments on heavy atoms.

Conclusion

Let us estimate the measurement time necessary for observation of the effect. To determine the degree of parity nonconservation P in a transition with partial probability B it is necessary to record $N \sim B^{-1} P^{-2}$ events.

If we use an ion beam with density ρ traveling with velocity v in a volume V with a cross section S and length l, the number of decays N of the level in time t in this volume is

$$N = \rho v S t [1 - \exp(-l/v \tau_p)],$$

where, τ_p is the total lifetime of the level $L_n(2p_{1/2})$. As a result we obtain the following expression for the time of observation t:

$$t = \tau / V \rho B P^2$$

where

$$\tau = l/v [1 - \exp(-l/v \tau_p)]^{-1} = l/v (\tau_p \ll l/v) \quad \text{or} \quad \tau_p (\tau_p \gg l/v)$$

In the case of experiments with ion we have $v \sim 10^8$ cm/sec, $\rho \sim 10^5$ cm⁻³, and for our transition we find $\tau \sim l/v$.

If we assume $B \sim 10^{-5}$ this gives $t \sim (10^7 / V [cm^3])$ sec. Hence it follows that to obtain an acceptable observation time $t \sim 10^3$ sec it is necessary to use a volume $V \sim 10^4$ cm³

REFERENCES

1. Dmitry Budker, Parity nonconservation in atoms, University of California, Berkeley, 1999.

2. D. Haidt, A. Pullia, The weak neutral current - discovery and impact Parity violation ,DESY, Hamburg, University Bicocca, Milano, 2012,
3. K.S. Babu, Parity violation , Oklahoma State University, SLAC, Summer Institute, SLAC,2022.
4. A. N. Moskalev, R. M. Ryndin, and I. B. Khriplovich, Usp. Fiz. Nauk 118, 409 (1976) [Sov. Phys. Uspekhi 19, 220 (1976)]
5. V. AL Alekseev, B. Ya. Zel'dovich, and I. I. Sobelman, Usp. Fiz. Nauk 118, 385 (1976) [Sov. Phys. Uspekhi 19, 207 (1976)],
6. V. G. Gorshkov, Preprint no. 268, LIYaF (Leningrad Nuclear Physics Institute) (1976).
7. L. N. Labzovskii, Izv. Akad. Nauk. SSSR Ser. Fiz. 41, 2491 (1977) [Bull. Acad. Sci, USSR 41 (1977)].
8. A.N, Moskalev, Material from the Thirteenth Winter School on Nuclear and Elementary Particle Physics, Leningrad, 1978 (Part 4, p. 192).
9. V.G. Gorshkov, A.I. Mikhailov, and A. N. Moskalev, Zh. Eksp. Teor. Fiz. 69, 1507 (1975) [Sov. Phys. JETP 42, 769 (1975)]
10. V. G. Gorshkov, G. L, Klimchitskaya, L. N. Labzovskii, and M. Melibaev, Izv. Akad. Nauk SSSR Ser. Fiz. 41, 2502 (1977) 3 (Bull. Acad. Sci, USSR, Phys, Ser, 41 (1971)].
11. S. Weinberg, Phys, Rev.D5, 1412 (1972).
12. J. A, Bearden, Rev. Mod. Phys. 39, 78 (1967).
13. H. Scofield, Atomic Data and Nuclear Data Tables, 14, no. 2 (1974)
14. I, M. Band, M. B, Trzhaskovskaya, and V. I, Fomichev, Preprint no, 299, LIYaF (1977),